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EVALUATING A NURSE PRACTITIONER-LED TELEHEALTH FOR MEDICARE
ADVANTAGE (THV-MA) PROGRAM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Some older adults lack access to healthcare. Access issues were exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for older adults. Seniors' lack of routine primary care visits for chronic disease management and preventive screenings, resulting in gaps in care, is concerning. To address access to care issues and care gaps, many organizations converted face-to-face visits to telehealth visits (THV). This DNP project provides a program evaluation of the effectiveness of an existing Telehealth for Medicare Advantage (THV-MA) program to identify the program's strengths and areas for improvement and make recommendations for expansion of the program to other regions within the organization. Method: Using the Logic Model and STEM telehealth program measurement domains as a guide, retrospective data were analyzed to determine whether the telehealth program's outcome indicators of healthcare access, care gap closure, and patient satisfaction were met from April 2023 through August 2023. Results: Of the 3,021 patients contacted, 164 (5.4%) agreed to a THV and scheduled an appointment. Two barriers, no smart device, or physical limitations, affected 10% of patients and resulted in an unscheduled THV. A point biserial correlation analysis indicated that older patients tend not to schedule THV. Of scheduled visits, 119 were completed, translating to nearly 73%. A total of 94% of patients had one or more care gaps closed during the THV. The THV-MA program had high patient satisfaction, with 45% of the patients completing the telephone survey. The most frequent single-word description of the THV-MA program was "thorough."

Keywords: Medicare Advantage, telehealth, older adult, Logic Model, STEM Framework, program evaluation, access to care, care gaps, preventive screening, patient satisfaction.

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Background

Many older adults with complicated medical problems in the United States lack adequate healthcare access (Hawley et al., 2020). As defined by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, access to healthcare is the prompt utilization of medical care that leads to optimal results (U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion [ODPHP], n.d.). Barriers to accessing healthcare include inadequate health insurance, lack of transportation, and reduced healthcare resources (ODPHP, n.d.). These barriers can result in expensive, preventable late-stage diseases (Bierman et al., 2021).

When the COVID-19 pandemic occurred, healthcare and access were heavily impacted worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). Some of the most vulnerable patient populations were disproportionately affected (Hacker et al., 2021). One such group was Medicare beneficiaries (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services [CMS], 2022). Medicare Advantage members are particularly vulnerable since they tend to be older, have lower incomes, and are more ethnically diverse than regular Medicare consumers (America's Health Insurance Plans, 2021). Medicare Advantage or Medicare Part C is a health maintenance organization alternative to traditional Medicare for senior health insurance coverage (American Association of Retired Persons, 2023). In 2022, nearly 50% of all Medicare-eligible enrollees were covered by Medicare Advantage plans (Freed et al., 2022).

According to Boccuti et al. (2013) of the Kaiser Family Foundation, those who fall into vulnerable Medicare demographics—such as minorities, people with low socioeconomic status, people whose health is deteriorating, and people who have at least five chronic diseases—are less likely to see a doctor. The lack of routine primary care visits by seniors with multiple

chronic conditions is a concern, especially in light of COVID-19. In addition to the pandemic restrictions impeding access to routine medical care, approximately 41% of adult patients in the United States postponed healthcare visits due to COVID-related concerns (Czeisler et al., 2020). As a result, many patients remain behind with chronic disease management and preventive screenings (Hacker et al., 2021). Despite some recovery after initial COVID-19 shutdowns, cancer screening rates are roughly 25% lower than baseline rates (Miller et al., 2021). Providing preventive care can help older adults prevent or slow the progression of disease and disability, thus reducing health risks and costs (Centers for Disease Control & Prevention [CDC], n.d.).

Failing to keep up to date with recommended preventive care, known as a care gap, is defined as the difference between recommended and delivered care (Carman et al., 2019). In the quality improvement realm, these care gaps can include breast and colon cancer screenings and screenings for blood pressure, depression, and fall risk. In some organizations, reassessing chronic diseases is also considered a gap in care. Nurse practitioners (NPs) can play a significant role in providing care for elderly patients. Furthermore, NPs are successfully utilized to improve access and address care gaps, particularly for marginalized and vulnerable populations (Hakimjavadi et al., 2022). The growth of telehealth offers continued opportunities to improve access to healthcare.

Many organizations converted face-to-face visits to telehealth visits (THV) to address care gaps and access during COVID-19. Telehealth or telemedicine refers to utilizing a broad range of communication technologies such as audio, video, text messaging, apps, or a combination of these mediums to access healthcare services remotely (Rush et al., 2018). THVs have existed for decades. However, these visits have increased in frequency and popularity since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for older adults. From 2019 to 2020, THVs

by Medicare enrollees increased from approximately 840,000 to 52.7 million, which is a 63-fold increase (United States Department of Health & Human Services, 2021). Studies included in a systematic review by Batsis et al. (2019) concluded that THVs are an effective modality for improving access to care and providing care to older adults.

Decreased access to primary care providers has made getting patients up to date with care challenging. Innovative solutions are being called upon to address access and care gaps for individuals with multiple chronic conditions (Bierman et al., 2021; Loewenson & Simpson, 2017). Healthcare providers, including NPs, who integrate telehealth into everyday clinical practice can address these access-to-care challenges (Batsis et al., 2019). Therefore, in 2022, a large healthcare system in California launched the Telehealth for Medicare Advantage (THV-MA) Program. The purpose was to build an internal process to address Medicare Advantage patients' healthcare access and care gaps when they could not be resolved during in-person primary care visits by completing a THV with an NP. The underlying premise was that THVs are another tool to screen patients, close care gaps, and reevaluate chronic conditions.

Since this THV program's inception, data has been collected to understand utilization patterns and performance around closing care gaps. An evaluation of this program was needed to determine whether it was meeting its goals and to determine how satisfied patients were with the THV experience.

Purpose Statement

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to evaluate the existing THV-MA program's outcome measures in a large, non-profit healthcare organization's California region. Specifically, the focus was on analyzing retrospective data to determine whether the telehealth program's outcome indicators of healthcare access, care gap closure, and patient satisfaction were

met from April 2023 through August 2023. The objective was to identify the program's advantages as well as any potential areas for improvement. In addition, results and recommendations were shared with key organizational stakeholders.

Conceptual Framework

A *conceptual framework* is a roadmap that is needed to guide projects (Bonnell & Smith, 2021). Frameworks are crucial because they categorize ideas, define concepts, and clearly depict how processes and results are related (Bonnell & Smith, 2021). In other words, the framework connects the various project components. The Logic Model (LM) provides the structure to guide this DNP project (Appendix A).

Logic Model

The LM is a framework that Joseph Wholey first published in 1979 and has been modified numerous times (University of Wisconsin-Madison, n.d.). In its simplest form, the LM is a systematic way to visually communicate and demonstrate an understanding of how the available resources, the program activities, and the outcomes sought are related (W.K. Kellogg Foundation [WKKF], 2004). Logic models are helpful for various purposes, including designs, plans, communication, evaluation, and learning, and are regularly used to clarify concepts, overcome obstacles, or measure progress (Knowlton & Phillips, 2012). For evaluation, logic models explain the intended plan and the anticipated outcomes (Knowlton & Phillips, 2012).

The LM is commonly used in program evaluations as it allows for a thorough project examination (McCoy & Castner, 2020). There are many examples of using the LM for program evaluation. Pang et al. (2020) created an LM framework to design and evaluate nutrition support interventions for cancer patients. Additionally, the LM has been used to assess the results of patient engagement programs (Merker et al., 2022). Osuch et al. (2019) utilized the LM to

evaluate the outcomes of an adult mood and anxiety treatment program. When used in conjunction with evaluation, the LM produces improved outcome reporting, more learning opportunities, and insight into program effectiveness (WKKF, 2004).

LM Definitions

The LM comprises five primary components: inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact. *Inputs* are also known as resources, such as stakeholders, funding, and participants. *Activities* are the interventions implemented during the program. *Outputs* are the end results of the activities performed. *Outcomes* are the metrics that the program will use to gauge its success, such as tracking completion rates and customer satisfaction polls. *Impact* measures the outcomes over short, intermediate, and long-term intervals. The core elements of the LM illustrate the relationship between the program and the desired results (WKKF, 2004).

Application of LM to THV-MA Program Evaluation

In this DNP project, the LM was utilized to evaluate the overall effectiveness of an existing NP-led THV program. One foundational aspect of the LM includes addressing assumptions. Defining stakeholder assumptions regarding how and why a project will address a specific issue, exploring new avenues, and maximizing valuable resources are essential to quality evaluation and program success (WKKF, 2004). The assumption for this program was that THVs are another tool to screen patients, close care gaps, and reevaluate chronic conditions. A second foundational element is to consider barriers that could limit the program's overall success (WKKF, 2004). The barriers to the program evaluation process for this project included patients who did not have a smart device or did not agree to a callback survey.

Inputs

For the THV program, *inputs* include leadership stakeholders, running a pursuit list of

patients with outstanding care gaps, hiring two outreach coordinators to schedule patients, and one NP to conduct the THV. For this program evaluation, it was necessary to evaluate if resources are used appropriately and effectively.

Activities

Activities are the specific interventions used (WKKF, 2004). For the THV program, these are divided into training for the outreach coordinators and training for the NP. The outreach coordinators received training on explaining the purpose of the THV program to prospective patients using a script, scheduling patients in the electronic medical record (EMR) and assisting patients with connecting to the videoconferencing platform Zoom for the appointment. Training for the NP was conducted regarding the purpose of the THV program, how to use the EMR, and the components of the THV, such as screening tests, identifying and closing care gaps, and assessing chronic conditions. In evaluating the THV program, assessing whether activities took place as intended was essential.

Outputs

Outputs are the direct results or impact of the activities (WKKF, 2004). Therefore, the outputs for this program are: THV conducted, appropriate screening tests and care gaps completed, and chronic diseases assessed. This data is valuable as it helps specify outcomes or immediate objectives (WKKF, 2004). This project compared the results of the activities against what was expected.

Outcomes

Outcomes and impact are the anticipated effects in terms of time (WKKF, 2004). These are divided into short-, intermediate, and long-term outcomes. Increased access to clinicians and assessment of chronic health conditions were the short-term outcomes identified for the THV

program. The intermediate outcomes included improvements to the THV program based on the evaluation results and expanding the THV program to other regions. Even though this program evaluation was not completed in a timeframe that could evaluate the long-term effects of the THV program, organizational leaders anticipated decreased morbidity and mortality through fall prevention and chronic disease management efforts.

Summary

In summary, the LM is a valuable project performance tool that effectively evaluates activities, outputs, and outcomes (Hayes et al., 2011). Moreover, it facilitates ongoing program improvement. Evidence from the literature lends support to using the LM as the framework to direct and aid in this program evaluation. Due to the LM's proven effectiveness as a conceptual framework, this DNP project utilized this model to organize and guide the program evaluation process.

Review of Literature

Overview

This DNP project aimed to evaluate an existing telehealth program in a large healthcare organization in Southern California. A literature review was conducted using the PubMed and Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health (CINAHL), Elton B. Stephens Company (EBSCO), and Google Scholar electronic databases. The search was limited to peer-reviewed, full text available in English from 2016-2022. The key search words in various combinations used were telehealth, telemedicine, older adults, chronic disease, multiple chronic conditions, access to care, fall risk screening or assessment, care gaps, patient satisfaction, and telehealth program evaluation. Additionally, snowball searching was completed by searching articles referenced in systematic reviews and annotated bibliographies to find additional relevant studies.

A total of 22 relevant published studies were found and used for this project. The 22 studies include three systematic reviews (Batsis et al., 2019; Rush et al., 2018; Şahin et al., 2021), two randomized controlled trials (Friedman et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2016), two cohorts (Chen et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al., 2021), two quasi-experimental (Jezewski et al., 2022; Nithman, 2018), ten descriptive (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Dang et al., 2018; Garner et al., 2022; Howland et al., 2018; Juergens et al., 2022; Lam et al., 2020; Mark et al., 2020; Price et al., 2022; Roberts & Mehrotra, 2020; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021), one mixed methods (Bhatia et al., 2022), and two qualitative (Dryden et al., 2023; Meekes et al., 2022). Most studies included in the review of literature were based in the United States; however, three included studies were from Europe and one from Canada. All studies, whether focusing on patients, clinicians, or claims data, were carried out in the outpatient setting.

This existing THV program has not been evaluated previously. This literature review focuses on topics related to how telehealth is used and evaluated. Key themes within the research included in this review are categorized under the following headings: telehealth, use of telehealth in older adults, ways to use telehealth, patient satisfaction with telehealth, use of telehealth to address care gaps, use of telehealth for chronic disease management in older adults, use of telehealth for preventive cancer screening in older adults, use of telehealth for fall risk screening in older adults, and evaluation of telehealth programs.

Telehealth

Telehealth or telemedicine refers to utilizing a broad range of communication technologies such as audio, video, text messaging, apps, or a combination of these mediums to access healthcare services remotely (Rush et al., 2018). Over the past several decades, telehealth has gradually grown as an alternative to in-person medical care. Utilization levels for telehealth increased due to COVID-19, stabilizing at 38 times higher than before the beginning of COVID-19, which now accounts for 13 to 17 percent of visits across all specialties (Bestsenny et al., 2021). The sustained post-pandemic utilization of telehealth supports its continued use for medical care.

Telehealth has been used to improve access and deliver healthcare services to older adults, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Several systematic reviews discussed telehealth's effectiveness (Batsis et al., 2019; Rush et al., 2018; Şahin et al., 2021). Furthermore, many studies have evaluated the efficacy of telehealth for managing chronic diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, migraine headaches, type 2 diabetes, and heart failure in this population, and the health outcomes comparable to usual care (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Friedman et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2016; Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al.,

2021). Chen et al. (2021) and Price et al. (2022) examined the role of telehealth in cancer screening. Several studies evaluated fall prevention practices in this population (Garner et al., 2022; Howland et al., 2018; Mark et al., 2020; Meekes et al., 2022; Nithman, 2018). These studies focused on feasibility, screening practices, and patient experience.

Ways to Use Telehealth

Telehealth can be carried out in several different ways. The method utilized can affect outcomes, including satisfaction. A systematic review concluded that compared to telephone-only appointments, video THV resulted in more accurate diagnoses and decision-making by physicians and fewer medication errors (Rush et al., 2018). Other studies have also found differences in video versus telephone visits (Juergens et al., 2022; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021). Some studies have found that telephone THVs are less effective than video. Juergens et al. (2022) conducted a retrospective, cross-sectional study of 273,301 video and telephone encounters and found a statistically significant ($p < .05$) difference in clinician prescribing and ordering practices between the two groups, especially in skin and soft tissue conditions. These findings imply that the clinical observations from video THV assist with the medical decision-making process and resultant treatment. Similarly, Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al. (2021) studied patients with heart failure and found that video visits had a significantly lower association with subsequent acute care hospital visits than telephone-only visits at 30 and 90 days ($p = 0.031$ & $p = 0.002$, respectively). The evidence from these studies supports using video over the telephone for THV.

Barriers to Telehealth in Older Adults

Many factors must be considered when examining the barriers to THV, especially in the older adult population. Barriers to telehealth care can be separated into technology, user-specific

factors such as dementia or sensory impairments like diminished vision and hearing, and lack of physical exam capabilities. In order to successfully complete a synchronous video telehealth visit, one must have a smart device such as a cell phone, tablet, or computer, a reliable internet connection, and knowledge of how to use them. Several researchers found technical issues such as a lack of internet-capable devices, inadequate internet connection, and a knowledge deficit on how to use technology as barriers associated with telehealth use in older adults (Aashima et al., 2021; Bhatia et al., 2022; Dryden et al., 2023; Lam et al., 2020; Şahin et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021). A national cross-sectional survey of 638,830 Medicare beneficiaries showed that 26.3% did not have a home device or internet connection, reducing the likelihood of participating in a THV (Roberts & Mehrotra, 2020). Roberts and Mehrotra (2020) also reported that communities of color, seniors over 85, and low socioeconomic status have even less access to technology. In addition to age, race, and low income, Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al. (2021) found that reduced use of video THVs was associated with not having a college degree, spouse, or significant other. These findings are unsurprising because there are costs connected with technology, and older people are frequently no longer employed and live on a fixed income.

In addition to citing technological difficulties, several studies also reported other barriers to using THVs (Aashima et al., 2021; Lam et al., 2020; Şahin et al., 2021). A cross-sectional study by Lam et al. (2020) also found that older patients were less prepared for THV due to physical issues that are more prevalent among them, such as hearing, vision, communication, or memory impairment. Similarly, Şahin et al. (2021) found that impaired hearing and inability to conduct physical exams were challenges to THV. Aashima et al. (2021) also supported these findings; their review included ten studies that reported technical difficulty and thirteen that reported a lack of hands-on examinations as the main challenges associated with THV and yet

still had high patient satisfaction regardless of age. A quasi-experimental study by Jezewski et al. (2022) sought to promote THV and decrease associated barriers in a vulnerable population of minority, low-income, elderly patients by implementing a THV education program. A pre-post survey design was used, and educational materials were given to 630 of those in the target population (Jezewski et al., 2022). In contrast to other surveys, 93% of older adults reported having access to an internet-compatible device. Technology access increases over time, which could explain the mixed results. According to a systematic review by Kruse et al. (2020) on telehealth utilization barriers, removing barriers will likely lead to an increase in the number of older persons using telehealth.

Patient Satisfaction with Telehealth

In addition to healthcare outcomes and effectiveness, examining patient satisfaction and experiences with THV and how satisfaction is evaluated is crucial. Studies report that patients are overall satisfied with THV (Bhatia et al., 2022; Dang et al., 2018; Dryden et al., 2023; Şahin et al., 2021). Two descriptive and one qualitative study found high patient satisfaction with THV (Bhatia et al., 2022; Dang et al., 2018; Dryden et al., 2023). Furthermore, Dang et al. (2018) found that 91% of caregivers and 65% of veterans favored video visits over in-person visits. Lastly, a systematic review by Şahin et al. (2021) included six studies, three randomized controlled trials, and three observational studies examining older adult satisfaction with THV. In one randomized controlled trial, participants expressed a favorable view, while the other five studies had a high degree of patient satisfaction (Şahin et al., 2021). Şahin et al. (2021) found that the convenience of THV over in-person visits overshadowed the barriers associated with its use in older adults, such as technological difficulties, impaired hearing, and inability to conduct physical exams.

Most studies used questionnaires to evaluate patient satisfaction (Bhatia et al., 2022; Dang et al., 2018; Şahin et al., 2021). Of these, none used validated patient satisfaction surveys. Unlike the study by Dang et al. (2018), which had patients complete the patient satisfaction survey by telephone, Bhatia et al. (2022) used a self-administered electronic satisfaction survey with both closed- and open-ended questions. In contrast, Dryden et al. (2023) performed semi-structured individual interviews with participants over the phone or video conference to assess patient satisfaction. These findings corroborate that overall, patients are satisfied with THV, and satisfaction can be evaluated using questionnaires.

Use of Telehealth to Address Care Gaps

In 2011, Medicare started paying for annual wellness visits, which are intended to promote preventive care and minimize health risks in older people by including criteria like depression and fall risk screening, which is not typically addressed by other preventive visits (Ganguli et al., 2018). The following year, the CMS developed quality performance measures for the Medicare Advantage program to ensure enrollees receive superior medical care, such as care coordination, cancer screenings, evidence-based treatments, and health promotion activities (CMS, 2012). Preventive healthcare decreases the risk of developing diseases, becoming disabled, and dying, yet millions of Americans fail to receive preventive care (ODPHP, n.d.).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the CMS and CDC recommended a temporary deferment of non-acute in-person medical care, including routine preventive care and screening, to lessen the risk to the public's health (Warner, 2021). As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, many patients are behind with chronic disease management and preventive screenings (Hacker et al., 2021), and telehealth can assist with closing these gaps in care. No studies were found that specifically address the use of telehealth to address care gaps. However, several studies

discussed the use of telehealth in chronic disease management, preventive care, and fall screening (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Friedman et al., 2019; Garner et al., 2022; Howland et al., 2018; Meekes et al., 2022; Nithman, 2018; Price et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2016; Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021).

Use of Telehealth for Chronic Disease Management in Older Adults

Chronic medical conditions like dementia, heart disease, type 2 diabetes, arthritis, and cancer are the primary causes of disease, disability, death, and healthcare expenses, which increase with age (CDC, 2022). Current data indicates that the vast majority, almost 95%, of older Americans have one chronic disease, and almost 80% have two or more (National Council on Aging, 2022). COVID-19 impacted chronic disease management as people shied away from visiting healthcare providers. In fact, among Americans with two or more chronic diseases, it has been reported that nearly 55% postponed or avoided seeking medical care (Czeisler et al., 2020).

The management of chronic conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, migraine headaches, type 2 diabetes, and heart failure has shown to be effective with telehealth interventions (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Friedman et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2016; Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021). Three studies showed that treatment outcomes with video THV were comparable or superior to in-person, usual care (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Friedman et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2016;). Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al. (2021) had similar findings but included both video and phone visits when comparing THV to in-person visits. The descriptive study by Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al. (2021) compared the outcomes of telephone visits versus video THVs and found a statistically significant, <0.05 , correlation between phone visits and the need for subsequent acute care treatment. In other

words, patients participating in video THVs had better outcomes than those completing phone visits.

The major weakness of Carotenuto et al. (2018), Friedman et al. (2019), and Rasmussen et al. (2016) was the sample sizes of 40 or fewer patients, which decreased the generalizability of the findings. In contrast, Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al. (2021) and Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al. (2021) had larger sample sizes of 8,263 and 3,570 unique patients, respectively. Despite study limitations, there is substantial evidence that chronic medical diseases can be managed effectively through THVs.

Use of Telehealth for Preventive Cancer Screening in Older Adults

Cancer screening in primary care is essential to detect and treat cancer earlier, translating to early cancer detection and treatment with decreased morbidity and mortality (Price et al., 2022). Telehealth is used to remind patients about cancer screenings, place mammogram orders, or make referrals to gastroenterologists for colonoscopies. Research examining COVID-19's impact on cancer screening practices found reductions (Chen et al., 2021; Price et al., 2022). A retrospective cohort study examined the association between breast, colon, and prostate cancer screening rates in adults aged 50-79 and COVID-19 in the United States (Chen et al., 2021). Chen et al. (2021) found declines in screening for each malignancy compared to 2019 data, but by July 2020, U.S. screening rates had nearly recovered to pre-pandemic levels. Moreover, despite resumed screenings, there remains a total deficit of nearly 4 million each for breast and colon cancers and 1.6 million for prostate cancer related to the pandemic (Chen et al., 2021). Price et al. (2022) conducted a descriptive study to assess primary care provider perspectives on the effect of telehealth and COVID-19 on cancer screening. Of the 757 physician respondents, nearly 35% reported delayed cancer screening during COVID-19 but have returned to their

previous screening routine (Price et al., 2022). Additionally, over half of those surveyed believe disruptions in screening practices will result in an increased occurrence of advanced cancer (Price et al., 2022).

Lastly, both study researchers found that telehealth can be used for preventive cancer screenings (Chen et al., 2021; Price et al., 2022). Given the evidence that there is an overall cancer screening deficit caused by COVID-19 and the importance of cancer screenings, using telehealth to assist with closing these care gaps is essential. Using telehealth to help close these care gaps is crucial, given that cancer screening is essential, and COVID-19 has resulted in an overall deficit in cancer screenings.

Use of Telehealth for Fall Risk Screening in Older Adults

In the U.S., falls account for most fatal and nonfatal injuries suffered by people 65 and older (Eckstrom et al., 2021). According to the CDC (2023), 28% of older adults experience a fall annually. Longevity, having many chronic illnesses, and taking multiple daily prescriptions are factors that raise the likelihood of falls in the elderly population (Mark et al., 2020). Furthermore, older people commonly experience decreased mobility, loss of independence, and fear of falling after a fall, which increases their risk for subsequent falls (Eckstrom et al., 2021). Evidence has shown that fall risk screening of seniors effectively decreases falls (Howland et al., 2018; Sarmiento & Lee, 2017). Therefore, preventive screening for fall risk in this population is crucial.

Several studies have been done examining the fall screening beliefs of healthcare providers. Primary care providers recognize that fall risk assessments and prevention are necessary, effective, and beneficial (Howland et al., 2018; Meekes et al., 2022). In a descriptive study by Howland et al. (2018), primary care providers were surveyed regarding fall prevention

practices focusing on these four factors: beliefs, expertise, attitudes, and assessment experiences. Of the 97 respondents, 87% thought they could successfully lower older individuals' risk of falling, and 96% indicated that all older persons should have their fall risk evaluated (Howland et al., 2018). Meekes et al. (2022) conducted a qualitative study exploring the barriers and facilitators associated with implementing fall risk screening and prevention interventions for general practitioners and nurses. In the two focus groups, all participants agreed that fall prevention is a responsibility of theirs and that this work is vital and beneficial (Meekes et al., 2022).

Providers incorporating fall prevention assessments into outpatient visits is reportedly low (Meekes et al., 2022; Sarmiento & Lee, 2017). Three studies examined provider fall risk screening practices (Howland et al., 2018; Mark et al., 2020; Meekes et al., 2022). Survey data from two different studies that involved primary care providers (PCPs) demonstrated that only about fifty percent of providers reported regularly assessing the fall risk of their older adult patients and having assessed approximately half of their elderly patients for a history of falls during the previous year (Howland et al., 2018; Mark et al., 2020). Similarly, Meekes et al. (2022) participants reported barriers contributing to low fall risk assessments as time-consuming, complicated, not a priority, and not incorporated into their practice.

A solution for expanding fall risk screening for older adults is telehealth. Two studies have examined the feasibility of performing fall screenings virtually (Garner et al., 2022; Nithman, 2018). The purpose of this observational feasibility study by Garner et al. (2022), which was part of a broader fall prevention research project, was to determine whether telehealth fall screenings for older persons could be carried out successfully and safely and to test a referral algorithm. The researchers found that 95% of virtual screening tests were completed without

adverse events or technological problems and concluded that telehealth fall screenings are feasible (Garner et al., 2022). Similarly, Nithman (2018) conducted a quasi-experimental study comparing virtual and in-person fall screening tools and concluded that telehealth is an effective way to assess fall risk and fall incidence among older adults living in the community. This evidence supports the importance of completing fall risk screening in older adults using telehealth.

Evaluation of Telehealth Programs

Program evaluations involve collecting data about a program's processes and outcomes and then analyzing them to determine whether the quality improvement initiatives accomplish their intended goals. Another component of the evaluation process is to assess sustainability (WHO, 2016). According to the National Quality Forum [NQF] (2021) and WHO (2016), a framework is crucial to measure the quality and effectiveness of telehealth programs. In 2017, the NQF built a framework to evaluate the effectiveness of telehealth programs that is divided into four domains: access to care, cost, experience, and effectiveness, to provide a method for establishing telehealth outcome measures (Chuo et al., 2020). The WHO framework for evaluating telehealth programs uses comparable measuring methods to the NQF but also makes provision for a telehealth program's development stage (Chuo et al., 2020).

Despite the surge in telehealth usage over the past few years, only three articles were found regarding structured ways to evaluate telehealth programs (Chuo et al., 2020; Chuo et al., 2021; Little et al., 2021). All three use the NQF domains as the foundation for their evaluation strategies. Two use the SPROUT Telehealth Evaluation and Measurement (STEM), which uses health outcomes, cost, experiences, and key performance indicators (KPIs) as the domains to evaluate telehealth and has been used in pediatric settings (Chuo et al., 2020; Chuo et al., 2021).

The other framework, Population/Health Outcomes, Access, Cost, and Experiences (PACE), was tailored to be used in the evaluation of occupational therapy telehealth programs (Little et al., 2021).

Surveys are the most popular method of evaluating telehealth programs. This evaluation method is practical for most healthcare settings because surveys can be quickly created and distributed (Li et al., 2022). A scoping review of 53 articles by Hajesmaeel-Gohari & Bahaadinbeigy (2021) found that the two most widely used questionnaires are the Telehealth Usability Questionnaire (TUQ) and the Telemedicine Satisfaction Questionnaire (TSQ). The TUQ is a comprehensive 21-item survey that measures the usefulness, ease of use and learnability, and connection quality of telehealth as well as reliability, satisfaction, and likelihood of future usage, and the TSQ, a 14-item survey to assess the level of patient satisfaction with using telehealth (Hajesmaeel-Gohari & Bahaadinbeigy, 2021). Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that surveys with fewer comprehensive questions achieve a more accurate assessment (Hajesmaeel-Gohari & Bahaadinbeigy, 2021).

Conclusion

The purpose of this literature review was to evaluate access to care and care gaps with telehealth in older adults and to identify strategies others use to evaluate the outcomes of telehealth programs. Telehealth can be a vital tool for healthcare providers to fulfill the needs of older adults. Literature supports this modality's effectiveness in addressing the Medicare population's preventive care and chronic disease management needs (Batsis et al., 2019). Preventive care and chronic disease management were adversely affected by COVID-19, resulting in fewer visits and delays in non-acute medical care. Utilizing telehealth can fill this gap as we continue to catch up with healthcare needs. Overall, for senior patients and healthcare

professionals, telehealth is effective, economical, and has high satisfaction levels (Aashima et al., 2021).

The literature also identified the need for telehealth programs to be evaluated using a standard format to ensure that the processes in place are producing the intended outcomes. Therefore, the STEM measurement domains were utilized to organize the indicators for this project's evaluation of an existing THV program. However, the health outcome domain was excluded because morbidity and mortality are beyond the scope of this DNP project.

Methods

Objective

This project aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of an existing telehealth program, identify the program's strengths and areas for improvement, and make recommendations to expand this telehealth visit program to other regions within the organization. This method section describes how the program evaluation was completed and includes the following subtopics: setting and sample, stakeholders and team members, an overview of the THV-MA program, design, ethical considerations, methods of evaluation, data collection, and data analysis.

Setting and Sample

The THV-MA program, launched in June 2022, was implemented at a large non-profit health system that spans seven states. Providence St. Joseph Health is composed of hospitals, clinics, provider offices, home health, and other affiliated medical services. The California service area is divided into three regions: Orange County/High Desert, Los Angeles area, and Northern California. Within each region, there are two types of medical groups. For this project, *medical groups* are defined as physicians and staff employed by Providence or one of its medical groups. On the other hand, *affiliate groups* are composed of physicians and staff whom Providence does not employ. Both group types see patients who are attributed to Providence by a health plan. There are approximately 94,000 patients enrolled in a Medicare Advantage plan, and nearly 10,000 have at least one care gap. The THV-MA program is described in detail below. For this program evaluation, the participants included were adult patients aged 65 and older with Medicare Advantage coverage who completed a synchronous video visit in the THV-MA program. Only patients who agreed to a callback were included in the patient satisfaction component. For patients who did not complete a THV, only demographic information restricted

to age, gender, region, type of group, and outcome of the outreach phone call was collected. Patients under 65 with a completed THV were excluded from this program evaluation.

Stakeholders and Team Members

The THV-MA Program was developed by the Executive Director of Risk Adjustment Programs and three leadership team members and approved by the California region's Chief Medical Officer. This program was based on the CMS Medicare Advantage quality measures and the risk adjustment model, which bases reimbursement on patient demographics and disease complexity, including chronic and comorbid conditions. Other stakeholders include the outreach coordinators and the NP.

Overview of THV-MA Program

The THV-MA program was created and implemented to build an internal process for Medicare Advantage patients to address healthcare access and care gaps by completing a THV with an NP when care gaps were not closed during an in-person visit. Eligible patients were identified by generating a quarterly pursuit list of those who have a known or suspected history of chronic disease who have not seen their PCP or completed a PCP visit and still have unassessed conditions for the current calendar year. Two outreach coordinators called patients identified in the report and offered to schedule a free telehealth visit appointment with the NP. The outreach coordinators confirmed with the patient that an internet-capable smart device would be available at the time of the visit. These coordinators were also responsible for keeping track of patient outreach status and contacting patients 10-15 minutes before their scheduled THV to ensure the patient could connect to the ZOOM™ appointment link and queue up the visit for the NP.

During the THVs, the NP closed applicable care gaps by assessing chronic conditions and completing a PHQ-9 depression screening and a STEDI fall risk screening; both questionnaires are embedded within the electronic medical record. The NP placed orders or referrals for positive screening results and offered appropriate screening tests to patients who were not current on colon or breast cancer screenings. Additional activities performed during the visit included reconciling the medication and problem lists and assessing blood pressure if the patient has a home blood pressure cuff. Lastly, patients with needs relating to social determinants of health, such as food insecurity or transportation difficulties, were referred to the care coordination department.

At the conclusion of the THV, patients were transitioned appropriately back to their PCP and encouraged to schedule a follow-up appointment for ongoing management. All visits were documented in the electronic medical record, and a copy of the progress note was faxed to the PCP. Care gaps were considered closed after screening tests, referral visits, or evaluations of chronic conditions were completed.

Design

The design for this DNP project is a program evaluation using quantitative and qualitative metrics to determine the effectiveness of meeting the THV-MA program goals: increased access to care, care gap closure, and patient care satisfaction. The THV-MA program evaluation was guided by the STEM concepts. These STEM measurement domains—health delivery, person experience, and program implementation and KPIs—align with the stated goals of the THV-MA program (Chuo et al., 2020) (Appendix B). Table 1 in Appendix B displays the questions that were used to evaluate the proposed program using the STEM measurement domains.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board approval from California State University, Fullerton, and the project site were obtained before initiating the data extraction and evaluation (Appendix C & D). This program evaluation was deemed as a quality improvement project, not research. Also, approval was obtained from the site's Chief Nursing Officer (Appendix E). This program evaluation contained minimal risks because de-identified and aggregated data will be used to safeguard the patients' anonymity. The de-identified data was provided to the project lead, who will complete the evaluation.

Methods of Evaluation

Access to care effectiveness was evaluated by tracking the number of completed THV between April 10- August 25, 2023. The effectiveness of the program in closing care gaps was determined by counting the number of care gaps closed including chronic disease assessment, depression, fall risk, and relevant cancer screening assessments completed during the THV. Patient satisfaction was evaluated by examining the results of a novel patient satisfaction telephone survey. This survey has been incorporated into the THV-MA program. At the end of the THV, the NP informed patients about the satisfaction survey and requested permission for a callback. For patients who previously agreed, the telephone survey was conducted approximately four to six weeks after the THV to allow time for any referrals to be addressed.

Instrument

Patient satisfaction was determined using the results of a new patient experience and satisfaction survey developed by the Center for Care Innovations (CCI), which partnered with the RAND Corporation, a well-known research and survey development company. The partnership's outcome was developing a survey toolkit to measure patient satisfaction with

telehealth. Although it has not been validated yet, the survey was adapted from this toolkit for use in this THV-MA program evaluation. The developers of this survey advocate customization and use of the survey as needed; therefore, access to it is free (CCI, 2020). During the callback, patients were asked to agree or disagree with four statements and answer three questions. The first four questions use a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly agree—Agree—Disagree—Strongly Disagree.

The statements are:

1. The nurse practitioner I saw during the telehealth visit explained things in a way that was easy to understand.
2. The nurse practitioner I saw over telemedicine spent enough time with me.
3. Overall, I was satisfied with this telemedicine visit.
4. I would participate in this telemedicine visit again.

The last three questions to answer are open-ended:

1. If a test was ordered during your visit, did you complete it? If not, why?
2. Any suggestions you have to improve this program?
3. Is there anything that I did not ask that you would like to share?

Data Collection

Data was provided to the project lead by data collectors. The data collectors performed a retrospective review of charts and patient satisfaction survey results for this program evaluation. Every patient who completed a THV through the THV-MA program from April 10 to August 25, 2023, was entered into an MS Excel® spreadsheet to track visits completed and record the following demographics: age, gender, medical group, or affiliate member. The EMR was reviewed to determine if chronic conditions were assessed, and screening assessments were

completed. Also, the MS Excel® file included referrals and tests ordered during the THV. If the patient had a home monitoring cuff, blood pressure was recorded to evaluate whether the less than 140/90 blood pressure-controlled quality care gap measure had been satisfied. Responses from a novel patient satisfaction telephone survey were recorded onto the spreadsheet.

Sequential numbering, starting with 1, was used to track patients; no further identifying information was input. Once the project was completed and disseminated, the MS Excel® spreadsheet was deleted.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were generated to examine patient demographics, visits completed, and the percentage of patients agreeable to a callback. Also, a descriptive analysis of care gaps closed, and the compliance rate with suggested screenings and referrals will be performed. Chi-square and point biserial correlational analyses will be used to evaluate any differences by age and gender groups. Mean satisfaction scores will be calculated for the quantitative patient satisfaction analysis, and thematic analyses will be used for the qualitative data. Data will be evaluated in an aggregate manner and displayed in tables and charts to assist with explaining results (Appendix F).

Evaluation

Since this THV-MA program's inception, data has been collected to understand telehealth utilization patterns, performance around closing care gaps, and patient satisfaction. However, no defined method or process was in place for assessing and monitoring the program's overall efficacy. Therefore, the purpose of this project is to evaluate the THV-MA program outcomes of healthcare access, care gap closure, and patient satisfaction as described in the methods section. The data will be analyzed to identify the program's strengths and areas for improvement.

Performance indicators, including patient satisfaction scores, THV completion rates, and the percentage of care gaps closed will be shared with the leadership team and other key stakeholders. Additionally, recommendations will be made should modifications to the program be warranted. It will also be recommended that the THV-MA program be reviewed quarterly to assess its ongoing effectiveness.

Results

Data analysis was performed using Intellectus Statistics™ software. The results of the four-month program evaluation are presented in the following sections: demographic data, access to care, care gap closure, and patient satisfaction.

Demographic Data

The total number of patients called was 3,021. The most frequently observed age group was 70-74 (27%). There were more females (58%). Most patients resided in the Orange County/High Desert area (78%), and over half (54%) were empaneled with an affiliate primary care physician, which is a physician not employed by a Providence medical group (Appendix G).

Access to Care

Of the 3,021 patients called, 164 (5.4%) agreed to a THV and scheduled an appointment (Appendix H, Table 1). Of those scheduled, 119 visits were completed, which translates to nearly 73% (Appendix H, Figure 1). The average number of patients seen per week was six (Appendix H, Figure 2).

A point biserial correlation analysis was performed to examine the association between the age of patients who scheduled a visit and those who did not. This statistical test measures the relationship between continuous and dichotomous variables (Hazra & Gogtay, 2016). A significant correlation was found and suggested that patients who do not schedule a THV tend to be older, with a correlation coefficient of .11 ($p < .001$, 95.00% CI [0.08, 0.15]) (Appendix H, Table 2). The Chi-square Test of Independence is used to determine if there are any differences between variables of what is expected and what is observed (Grove & Gray, 2019). In this instance, it was performed to look for differences between region and group type related to patient appointment scheduling behavior. The results showed that patients residing in the Los

Angeles area and Northern California were more likely to schedule an appointment, as were patients assigned to a Providence medical group primary care physician (Appendix H, Table 3 & Table 4, respectively). No significant association was found between gender and appointment scheduling (Appendix H, Table 5).

Barriers

Approximately 10%, or 278 patients, reported one of two barriers that prevented them from scheduling a THV appointment. Barriers included patients who did not have access to a smart device (n=244, 8.5%) or who needed assistance to complete the visit (n=34, 1.2%) (Appendix H, Table 1). The most common barrier was the lack of a smart device (Appendix H, Figure 3). A biserial correlation was performed between age and visit not scheduled due to lack of a smart device and all other reasons, which showed a significant positive correlation (Appendix H, Table 6). As a result, older age is associated with not scheduling an appointment due to a lack of a smart device.

Care Gap Closure

Figure 1 (Appendix I) shows the percentage of patients with at least one care gap closed during the THV and a breakdown of the tracked care gap categories. The Chi-square Test of Independence was performed to examine whether the variables of age and any care gap closed were related. The Chi-square test results were not significant based on an alpha value of .05, $\chi^2(4) = 5.40$, $p = .249$, and indicate that the variables are likely independent of each other (Appendix I, Table 1). The Chi-square test results were also not significant for a relationship between any care gap closed and either gender or region (Appendix I, Table 2 & 3, respectively).

As part of the post-visit survey, patients were asked, "If a test or referral was ordered during your visit, did you complete it? If not, why?" Of the 49 respondents who completed the

survey, only 25 had a test or referral ordered. Figure 2 (Appendix I) depicts the percentages of patients who did or did not complete the order, as well as patients who had an appointment scheduled or the referral was still in process. In addition, the "no" replies were examined and classified into three themes: reconsidered, illness, and needs assistance.

Theme 1: Reconsidered

"I changed my mind" – 70-74-year-old female

"I don't have time to attend classes" – 75-79-year-old male

Theme 2: Illness

"I am recovering from surgery first" – 80-84-year-old female

"Seeing other doctors because of shortness of breath and severe anemia, so I have not gone yet" – 80-84-year-old female

Theme 3: Needs Assistance

"I refused because I was concerned it was a spam call. I still want the referral" – 70-74-year-old female

"It was approved, but the provider did not answer. I need a referral for a different provider" – 85 and older aged male

All patients seen in the THV-MA program were assessed for gaps in preventive screening tests. Results of this project showed that 29 patients (24%) were current with fall risk screening, while 90 patients (76%) had an open care gap that was closed during the THV appointment (Figure 3, Appendix I). For colon cancer screening, 105 patients (88%) were found to be either up-to-date or no longer in the recommended age group for screening. Of the remainder, orders were placed for seven patients, two declined testing, and five had existing orders pending from the PCP (Figure 4, Appendix I). The results were similar for breast cancer screening, with 109

patients (92%) either up-to-date or screening not recommended due to age or gender. For the other ten patients, four mammograms were ordered, and the rest of the patients declined screening (Figure 5, Appendix I).

Patient Satisfaction

Quantitative

Initially, 108 patients agreed to a callback to participate in the satisfaction survey. All were called, but only 49 (45%) completed the survey. Participants reported high satisfaction with the THV-MA program, with mean scores ranging from 3.4-3.7 on a Likert scale of 1 (lowest) to 4 (highest), as shown in Figure 1, Appendix J (n=49).

Qualitative

Patients were asked two open-ended questions during the patient satisfaction survey phone call. First, 73% (36) of patients responded when asked, “Is there anything that I did not ask that you would like to share about the THV-MA program?” The responses were overwhelmingly positive. A word cloud was created to show respondents’ most frequently occurring words to describe the THV-MA program (Figure 2, Appendix J).

Additionally, these responses were analyzed and categorized into themes. These four common themes emerged among the respondents: thorough, good, valuable, and convenient.

Theme 1: Thorough

“Brilliant idea. An in-depth visit was great for me, and I’d imagine it takes some of the workload off of my primary physician”–70-74-year-old male

“Thorough visit. Satisfied. Grateful for a program like this”– 65-69-year-old female

“Detailed visit. I appreciate anyone trying to keep me healthy”–70-74-year-old male

Theme 2: Good

“Wonderful program. I felt more confident that Providence can meet my healthcare needs”– 70-74-year-old male

“I liked it. I didn’t feel rushed. It was my first telehealth visit”– 65-69-year-old female

“It was good. I appreciated the visit.”– 70-74-year-old female

Theme 3: Valuable

“Felt spoiled and valued. Very thorough”– 75-79-year-old male

“Helpful and informative”– 80-84-year-old male

“Very valuable”– 70-74-year-old male

Theme 4: Convenient

“I like that it is telehealth, so I don’t have to go into the office, which takes up more time.”–70-74-year-old male

“Overall, a positive experience. Thorough. The convenience of telehealth was a big plus for me.”– 65-69-year-old female

“Telehealth is a great option as a bedbound person.” – 75-79-year-old male

The second open-ended question posed was “Any suggestions you have to improve this program?” Only 11 (22%) of the 49 patients answered this question. Among the respondents, these three common themes were identified: lack of clarity, too detailed, and audio issues.

Theme 1: Lack of Clarity

“Be more clear in explaining. Information presented came across as life-threatening when it is not, and it scared me.”– 65-69-year-old female

“I was told immunizations were due, but the names were not included in the note, so I had to make a phone call to find out which ones were due.”–70-74-year-old female

Theme 2: Too Detailed

“Went into so much detail about past medical history that it ate up most of the visit time. While past history is important, that degree of detail seemed unnecessary.” –70-74-year-old female

“A little bit long. Should have just asked if my medications are up to date instead of spending so much time going over each one.” –70-74-year-old male

Theme 3: Audio Issues

“Audio was not loud enough.” –70-74-year-old female

“I am hard of hearing, and the NP had an accent that made it difficult for me to understand what she was saying.” –80-84-year-old male

Summary

Of the 3,021 patients contacted, 164 (5.4%) agreed to a THV and scheduled an appointment. Two barriers, no smart device or physical limitations, affected 10% of patients and resulted in an unscheduled THV. A point biserial correlation analysis indicated that older patients tend not to schedule THVs. Of scheduled visits, 119 were completed, translating to nearly 73%. Most patients, 94%, had one or more care gaps closed during the THV; fall risk screening and HCC diagnoses were the most commonly identified. Almost all patients were current with cancer screening tests before being seen in the THV-MA program. Of those requiring a test or referral order, 72% of patients had completed or were pending completion, while the other 28% did not follow through. High satisfaction was reported by those who participated in the post-THV-MA program survey, with 45% of the patients completing the telephone survey. The most frequent single-word description of the THV-MA program was "thorough."

Discussion

This DNP project aimed to evaluate the THV-MA program's effectiveness in increasing access to care, reducing care gaps, and measuring patient satisfaction using the STEM concepts as a guide. Even though the findings showed a slight increase in access for some patients, the THVs had high care gap closure and high patient satisfaction scores.

Access to Care

There was a low rate of scheduling appointments. In more than half of the outreach telephone calls, there was either no answer or a voicemail message was left. With the surge of unsolicited automated calls, it is not surprising that so many people would not answer a call from an unfamiliar phone number. Furthermore, many patients were only called once due to understaffing. Multiple outreach attempts may increase the likelihood of speaking with patients and scheduling THVs. Of the patients scheduled, 73% completed the visits, while the other 27% were either a no-show or a cancellation, which is a higher completion rate than a cohort study conducted by Eberly et al. (2020). In that study of 148,402 patients, only 54% completed a scheduled telemedicine appointment, which resulted in a 46% cancellation or no-show visit rate (Eberly et al., 2020). The difference between THV completion rates could be related to the THV-MA program staff confirming all appointments beforehand. Alternatively, THVs have been in higher use, and people are more acclimated to virtual visits.

Lack of internet-capable smart devices and physical conditions such as vision or hearing impairment are well-documented barriers to THV in older adults (Aashima et al., 2021; Batsis et al., 2019; Dryden et al., 2023; Lam et al., 2020; Şahin et al., 2021; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021). The results of this project also showed the same barriers. However, compared to a nationwide survey that revealed up to 26.3% of Medicare beneficiaries do not own a smart

device, the percentage of patients in this project without one was significantly lower at 8.5% (Roberts & Mehrotra, 2020). The discrepancy could be related to participants living in more affluent areas or because access to technology has increased over time. This project corroborated previous findings that the lack of a smart device rises as people get older (Roberts & Mehrotra, 2020; Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021). Three systematic reviews examined THV in older adults and suggest that removing barriers to THV is likely to increase the use of THV (Batsis et al., 2019; Kruse et al., 2020; Şahin et al., 2021).

Care Gaps

Overall, the THV-MA program was effective in closing care gaps as evidenced by 94% of patients seen had one or more care gaps closed. This finding is supported in the literature (Carotenuto et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Friedman et al., 2019; Garner et al., 2022; Howland et al., 2018; Meekes et al., 2022; Nithman, 2018; Price et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2016; Sammour, Spertus, Austin et al., 2021) and Sammour, Spertus, Shatla et al., 2021).

During the THVs, the most frequently closed care gap category was chronic diseases that had not been addressed yet during the 2023 calendar year. This is significant because Medicare Advantage payments are determined by patients' demographics, disease severity, and comorbidities (Prasad et al., 2021; Torres et al., 2019). In fact, CMS developed a list of diagnoses grouped into categories which are conditions associated with an increase in cost or patient risk known as Hierarchical Condition Categories (HCCs); (Torres et al., 2019). Kelley et al. (2017) compared the HCC model's projected cost of care to the actual Medicare expenditures and the monetary amounts were comparable. Since HCCs accurately predict the cost of care, healthcare providers must assess them annually. Therefore, gaps in care resulting from not addressing these chronic HCCs can cause significant, negative financial consequences (Smith &

Moore, 2017). In this project, 99 patients (83%) had at least one of these chronic conditions addressed which had not yet been addressed during the calendar year.

Fall risk screening is essential for older people to help prevent falls (Howland et al., 2018; Sarmiento & Lee, 2017). For Medicare Advantage patients, fall risk screening is a quality measure that studies show has a low completion rate (Howland et al., 2018; Sarmiento & Lee, 2017). The literature reports that approximately 50% of PCPs conduct fall risk screening for their older adult patients (Howland et al., 2018; Mark et al., 2020). However, in this DNP project, only 24% of patients had an up-to-date fall risk screening. As a result, the THV-MA program NP was able to close the fall risk screening care gap for the other 76% of patients. Timing is a possible explanation for the screening discrepancy. Because this project stopped collecting data in August of 2023, patients seen after were omitted and could have subsequently had the fall screening assessment.

This project's results indicate a low cancer screening care gap percentage. The literature regarding post-COVID-19 cancer screening rates is conflicting. Some literature reports that while initially decreased, cancer screening has been restored to pre-COVID levels (Chen et al., 2021; Price et al., 2022). However, Chen et al. (2021) also reported that a net pandemic-related cancer screening deficit remains. The difference could be because this project took place in 2023 while the two studies were done right after the pandemic had ended. The two studies were published shortly after the conclusion of the pandemic, while this project was conducted in 2023. This could account for the disparity.

Patient Satisfaction

This project's findings supported high patient satisfaction for THVs and are concordant with previous research studies (Bhatia et al., 2022; Carotenuto et al., 2018; Dang et al., 2018;

Dryden et al., 2023; Şahin et al., 2021). Like Dang et al. (2018), patients' open-ended responses about the THV-MA program corresponded with their numerical Likert scale answers. For example, the highest-rated statement, "The nurse practitioner I saw over telemedicine spent enough time with me," matched the most frequent single-word description of "thorough." For the second open-ended question, "Any suggestions you have to improve this program?", patients expressed improvement suggestions in three areas: lack of clarity, overly detailed, and audio issues. Similarly, despite high satisfaction, Dryden et al. (2023) reported that some participants thought that their instructions were unclear or ambiguous. Literature also reported that hearing impairment issues can be problematic during THVs (Lam et al., 2020; Şahin et al. 2021). While most participants were greatly satisfied with the duration and degree of detail of the THV-MA project, a few suggested that there was "too much detail" as something that could be improved. This finding was not found in the literature. In contrast, Friedman et al. (2019) reported that the length of THV appointments was significantly less than that of in-person office visits.

Limitations

There are several limitations of this DNP project. First was a lack of outreach staff to call patients during the four months that this program evaluation took place. Later in the year, an additional outreach coordinator was hired, which resulted in a doubling of the weekly average number of patients completing a THV. A second limitation was calling patients to ask the patient satisfaction survey questions. It is possible that patients would have been more honest had the survey been anonymous. Furthermore, Spanish-speaking patients were excluded from the satisfaction survey because the surveyor was not bilingual. It is possible that the level of satisfaction with the THV-MA program would have been different for non-English speaking patients. Another limitation was the short duration of this program evaluation. Therefore,

realizing intermediate and long-term outcomes was beyond the scope of this project. Similarly, while a PHQ-9 depression screening was completed during each THV, the analysis of that data was beyond the scope of this project.

Recommendations

Using THV to improve access to care and close care gaps for Medicare Advantage patients is a beneficial resource. Moreover, it is associated with high levels of patient satisfaction. Therefore, the THV-MA program is recommended to continue and expand to other regions within the organization. However, staffing numbers must be increased to ensure that all eligible patients are being called and that those individuals who were initially unreachable can receive follow-up efforts. Another recommendation is to explore ways to reduce patient barriers related to completing THVs.

In the future, it is recommended that the financial impact of addressing and closing CMS HCC diagnosis gaps be analyzed. Moreover, examining the potential cost savings of referring patients with positive fall risk screening to physical therapy to prevent costly hip fractures and other fall-related injuries is essential. Lastly, this project did not include tracking race or social determinants of health equity. Future program evaluations should incorporate these factors, given that they have been demonstrated to be barriers to accessing healthcare through THVs (ODPHP, n.d.).

Conclusion

The THV-MA program is an effective program for closing care gaps and is associated with high levels of patient satisfaction. Despite limitations incurred during this program evaluation, there was an increase in access to care for some patients. Furthermore, the majority

of patients who completed a THV had care gaps closed and were highly satisfied with the THV-MA program.

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Appendix A

Conceptual Framework for the Telehealth Visit Program Evaluation

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework for the Telehealth Visit Program Evaluation

Logic Model for Telehealth Visit (THV) Program

Note: PCP= Primary Care Provider; THV= Telehealth Visit. Adapted from the LM.

Appendix B

STEM Domains-THV-MA Goals & Inquiry Questions

Table 1

STEM Domains-THV-MA Goals & Inquiry Questions

STEM Domains/THV-MA Goals	Inquiry Questions
Health Delivery/ Care Gap Closure	<p>Is the THV-MA program effective at closing care gaps?</p> <p>Are there differences in closing care gaps for male versus female patients?</p> <p>Are there differences in closing care gaps for patients of different ages?</p>
Individual Experience/ Patient Satisfaction	<p>Are patients satisfied with the THV-MA program?</p> <p>What suggestions do patients have to improve the THV-MA program?</p>
Program Implementation and KPI/Access to Care	<p>What is the mean number of THV per month?</p> <p>Which patients are more likely to agree to telehealth visits?</p> <p>What are the barriers to telehealth visits?</p>

Appendix C

Organization IRB Approval

CLINICAL INQUIRY PROJECT – NOT RESEARCH DETERMINATION

September 22, 2023

Dear Kelley Scott:

On 9/22/2023, the Human Research Protection Program (HRPP) reviewed the following submission:

Title:	Telehealth Visit for Medicare Advantage (THV-MA) Program Evaluation
Project ID:	STUDY2023000762
Project Lead Name:	Kelley Scott
Funding Source:	None

The HRPP determined that this project, as submitted, does not meet the definition of research as defined in the federal regulations, and does not require IRB review. This determination is based only upon the information submitted.

The project may proceed as described in the documents submitted for review and in line with requirements listed below and on the next page.

This determination does not exempt you from following hospital policies and procedures as they relate to conduct of this project.

As the project was deemed not to be research, any presentations or publications discussing the project may not refer to it as a research study or state that the project received IRB approval, but rather refer to it as a Quality Improvement project, Evidence-Based Practice project, etc.

Should there be any questions, please contact the HRPP at: PSJHIRBDetermination@providence.org

Appendix D

University IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

October 6, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Kelley Scott

Application No. HSR-23-24-95

Study Title: Evaluating a Nurse Practitioner-led Telehealth for Medicare Advantage (THV-MA) Program

|

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 4. Secondary research for which consent is not required: Secondary research uses of identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, if at least one of the following criteria is met:

- (i) The identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens are publicly available;
- (ii) Information, which may include information about biospecimens, is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects, the investigator does not contact the subjects, and the investigator will not re-identify subjects;
- (iii) The research involves only information collection and analysis involving the investigator's use of identifiable health information when that use is regulated under 45 CFR

parts 160 and 164, subparts A and E, for the purposes of "health care operations" or "research" as those terms are defined at 45 CFR 164.501 or for "public health activities and purposes" as described under 45 CFR 164.512(b); or

(iv) The research is conducted by, or on behalf of, a Federal department or agency using government-generated or government-collected information obtained for nonresearch activities, if the research generates identifiable private information that is or will be maintained on information technology that is subject to and in compliance with section 208(b) of the E-Government Act of 2002, 44 U.S.C. 3501 note, if all of the identifiable private information collected, used, or generated as part of the activity will be maintained in systems of records subject to the Privacy Act of 1974, 5 U.S.C. 552a, and, if applicable, the information used in the research was collected subject to the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995, 44 U.S.C. 3501 et seq.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Appendix E

Organization Approval Letter

Providence Medical Foundation
200 West Center Street Promenade,
Suite 800
Anaheim CA 92805

Institutional Approval Letter

4/24/2023

This letter is to show that, I, Shelly Lummus, as the Chief Nursing Officer at Providence Medical Foundation, give permission to Kelley Scott, FNP-c (project lead) to conduct the project titled Medicare Advantage Telehealth Visit Program Evaluation in the following department: Risk Adjustment.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

(1) collect data: completed THV, age, gender, medical group or affiliate group, depression, fall risk and cancer screening, orders, referrals, blood pressure, chronic conditions assessed, patient phone number if agreed to callback, patient satisfaction responses.

(2) access necessary documents/data

(3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPAA, and research and research-related regulations at Providence Medical Foundation and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature: FNP-BC, EdD

Name: Shelly Lummus, Ed.D., FNP-BC

Title: Chief Nursing Office, Southern California

Contact Information: Shelly.Lummus@stjoe.org

Appendix F

Data Analysis Table

Table 1

Data Analysis Table

Inquiry Question	Data	Statistical Evaluation
Demographics	Age Gender Region Type of provider group	Descriptive frequencies Descriptive frequencies Descriptive frequencies Descriptive frequencies
Access to Care Domain		
What is the mean number of THV per week?	Number of completed THV	Mean per week
How many patients agree to telehealth visits?	# Patients sub-grouped by those who had visits & those who did not	% Patients completing THV-continuous variable sub-grouped by week-run chart
What are the barriers to telehealth visits?	# Patients with barriers Types of barriers	% Patients with barriers Point biserial correlation
Care Gap Closure Domain		
Is the THV-MA program effective at closing care gaps?	1. # Care gaps closed overall and by type 2. If a test/referral was ordered during your visit, did you complete it? If not, why?	% Patients who had a cap gap closed overall & by type % Patients completing an ordered test Thematic analysis
Are there differences in closing care gaps by gender?	% Care gaps closed filtered by gender	Chi-Square differences by gender
Are there differences in closing care gaps for patients of different ages?	% Care gaps closed filtered by age	Chi-Square differences by age
Patient Satisfaction Domain		
Are patients satisfied with the THV-MA program?	Likert questions:	Means for each question

What suggestions do patients have to improve the THV-MA program?

1. The nurse practitioner I saw during the telehealth visit explained things in a way that was easy to understand.
 2. The nurse practitioner I saw over telemedicine spent enough time with me.
 3. Overall, I was satisfied with this telemedicine visit.
 4. I would participate in this telemedicine visit again.
- Open-ended questions:
1. Any suggestions for improving the program?
 2. Is there anything that I did not ask that you would like to share about the program?

Thematic analysis

Appendix G

Demographic Data of Participants

Table 1

Demographic Data of Participants

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Age		
65-69	444	14.70
70-74	822	27.21
75-79	713	23.60
80-84	511	16.91
85 and older	531	17.58
Gender		
F	1742	57.66
M	1279	42.34
Region		
Orange County/High Desert	2345	77.62
Los Angeles Area	153	5.06
Northern California	523	17.31
Group Type		
Providence Medical Group	1378	45.61
Affiliated Primary Care Physician	1643	54.39

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Appendix H

Access to Care Results

Table 1

Appointment Data

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Appointment Scheduled		
No	2857	94.57
Yes	164	5.43
Appointment Status		
Seen	119	72.56
No Show	27	16.46
Canceled	18	10.98
Result of Outreach for Unscheduled		
Left Voicemail	1157	40.50
No Answer	545	19.08
Declined	722	25.27
No Smart Device	244	8.54
Upcoming PCP Appointment	71	2.49
Wrong Number	18	0.63
Patient Requested Callback	25	0.88
Patient Needs Assistance	34	1.19
Phone Disconnected	41	1.44

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Table 2

Point Biserial Correlations for Appointment Scheduled and Age

Combination	<i>r</i>	95.00% CI	<i>n</i>	<i>p</i>
Appointment Scheduled-Age	.11	[.08, .15]	3021	< .001

Table 3*Chi-Square Analysis Appointment & Region*

Region	Appointment Scheduled		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	No	Yes			
OCHD	2230[2,217.70]	115[127.30]	9.58	2	.008
LA	137[144.69]	16[8.31]			
NORCAL	490[494.61]	33[28.39]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed[Expected].**Table 4***Chi-Square Analysis Appointment & Group Type*

Group Type	Appointment Scheduled		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	No	Yes			
Medical Group	1280[1,303.19]	98[74.81]	13.98	1	< .001
Affiliated Group	1577[1,553.81]	66[89.19]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed[Expected].**Table 5***Chi-Square Analysis Appointment & Gender*

Gender	Appointment Scheduled		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	No	Yes			
F	1644[1,647.43]	98[94.57]	0.31	1	.577
M	1213[1,209.57]	66[69.43]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed[Expected].**Table 6***Point Biserial Correlations for No Smart Device and Age*

Combination	<i>r</i>	95.00% CI	<i>n</i>	<i>p</i>
No Smart Device -Age	.15	[.12, .19]	2857	< .001

Figure 1

MA-THV Patients Scheduled Versus Seen per Week

Figure 2

MA-THV Patients Seen per Week

Figure 3*Barriers to Scheduling THV*

Appendix I
Care Gap Results

Table 1

Chi-square Analysis Age & One or More Care Gaps Closed

<i>Age</i>	<i>One or More Care Gaps Closed</i>		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>			
65-70	40[38.59]	1[2.41]	5.40	4	.249
71-75	32[33.88]	4[2.12]			
76-80	23[22.59]	1[1.41]			
81-85	13[12.24]	0[0.76]			
86 and older	4[4.71]	1[0.29]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed[Expected].

Table 2

Chi-square Analysis Gender & One or More Care Gaps Closed

<i>Gender</i>	<i>One or More Care Gaps Closed</i>		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>			
M	48[47.06]	2[2.94]	0.55	1	.458
F	64[64.94]	5[4.06]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed[Expected].

Table 3

Chi-square Analysis Region & One or More Care Gaps Closed

<i>Region</i>	<i>One or More Care Gaps Closed</i>		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>			
OCHD	79[80.94]	7[5.06]	2.85	2	.240
NORCAL	23[21.65]	0[1.35]			
LA	10[9.41]	0[0.59]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

Figure 1*MA-THV Care Gaps Closed*

Figure 2*MA-THV Completed Referral or Test*

Figure 4*Colon Cancer Screening*

Appendix J

Patient Satisfaction Results

Figure 1

MA-THV Patient Satisfaction Survey Results

Figure 2*Patient Satisfaction Word Cloud*